

Education Quarterly Reviews

Demirbilek, Nesip, Atila, Fulya, and Korkmaz, Celalettin. (2021), The Concept of Social Justice from the Perspective of University Students. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4, No.3, 89-99.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.03.321

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

The Concept of Social Justice from the Perspective of University Students

Nesip Demirbilek¹, Fulya Atila², Celalettin Korkmaz³

¹ Department of Child Care and Youth Services, Genç Vocational High School, Bingöl University, Turkey. Email: ndemirbilek@bingol.edu.tr, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5133-7111>.

² Teacher/Deputy Director, Ministry of National Education, Turkey. Email: fulyaozer88@gmail.com, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8537-8808>.

³ Department of Educational Sciences, Faculty of Education, Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Turkey. Email: celalettinkorkmaz@gmail.com, ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7249-1070>

Correspondence: Celalettin Korkmaz, Department of Educational Sciences, Faculty of Education, Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Turkey. Tel: +903262456000. Email: ckorkmaz@mku.edu.tr

Abstract

The aim of this study is to reveal how university students conceptualize their perceptions of social justice. 393 university students were included as the sample of the research. An interview form was sent to the students online. The content analysis technique was used in the analysis of the data. As results, it was stated that every student is equal, opportunities are provided equally, there is no discrimination, social activities are equally benefited, every student is given the same rights, interests and needs are cared for, and every student is treated fairly. They expressed as the most unjust incidents are "necessity of distance education due to the Covid-19 pandemic," "getting unworthy points," "discrimination," "lack of justice in scoring," "unfair scholarship distribution" and "no course exemption." In addition, since it is not in the literature, a scale can be developed regarding the social justice perception levels of students studying in higher education.

Keywords: Social Justice, Equal Opportunity, Covid-19, Nepotism, University, Students

1. Introduction

Justice, as a concept, has a social character as a moral act, it expresses the position of the individual against the law in a democratic claim of rights. The concept appears to people in many areas of social life. One of the most important concepts that reinforce the existence of justice is equality. First, the members of a society must be politically equal. The differences between the wealth, races, colors, beliefs, and cultures of the members of the society should not disrupt the equality between individuals in political participation and decision-making processes. To talk about the concept of political equality, everyone who is affected by the decisions taken and who is a party to this process should have the freedom to express their opinions or make their voices heard. Equality under the law is very important in terms of building a just social order (Polat, 2007; Sunal, 2011).

Although it is quite difficult to define social justice, it is explained as the fairness of a society where resources are distributed equally, and all members are safe in terms of physical, mental, and social aspects. Social justice, in the simplest terms, is the fair distribution of blessings and burdens in the society. In other words, everybody in the society has a general opinion that there is a fair sharing (Bell, 2007; Sunal, 2011).

Social justice is the state of being just and equal to all its citizens in terms of fundamental rights and opportunities, which allows all members of a society to access the same level of protection, equal opportunities, obligations, social assistance equally and fairly (Barker, 1999; Craig, 2002). Social justice can be achieved through social welfare-oriented decisions made by individuals, institutions, and societies. As can be understood from this feature, social justice is done and maintained by people. Therefore, all processes can be objected, and the decisions taken may be disrupted (Todd, 2015).

In the development of pluralist democratic societies, social justice steps in the elimination of unfair and discriminatory practices that individuals face in social life and the creation of a more democratic society. Social justice understanding is effective in keeping people away from pressure with its liberating side (Boyles, Carusi, & Attick, 2009). The understanding of social justice, which is at the basis of the welfare states, aims to provide a minimum standard of living for everyone in the society. Social justice is fundamentally based on the redistribution of social resources and services. Not every individual in the society is in an equal position in accessing these services. For this reason, welfare states benefit from the professional knowledge and value of the social work discipline in the distribution of these resources and services in a way that ensures equal opportunity (Kaynak, 2017). However, according to the data of the World Bank, which includes the development indicators of the countries, today many countries, especially poor countries, experience various problems related to social justice. Considering fair distribution and social minimums, the average daily consumption in the world is around one dollar. There are many poor families living with an income below this value. Poverty lines, especially in economically weak countries, generally remain at a level that can provide basic nutritional support and living requirements. Particularly inadequate training opportunities: It causes children and young people to inequality of opportunity and to be unable to use their rights in social life due to poverty and gender prejudices. Millions of children around the world are out of school. While poor children are unlikely to enroll in school, most children in affluent households in poor developing countries do not attend any school. Although educational opportunities for girls are expanding, gender bias is greater in low-income countries. Poor families have had to reduce their children's school expenses and consumption expenditures on food and health resources (World Bank, 2010).

The common point that can be sought in the relationship between education and justice stems from the characteristics of both being a social phenomenon, that is, aiming / creating a democratic common good in the society. At this point, the relationship between education and social justice is established spontaneously, and social justice in education refers to the fair use of education as a democratic right at both individual and social levels. Despite the egalitarian claims of modern societies, education is based on inequalities in many aspects, and in a system based on inequalities, it is important not what it is but what kind of meaning will be attributed to "social justice" in education. The basic point of conceptualizing social justice in education is that everyone should receive education according to their abilities and needs. Social justice in education is often expressed as equal education for all. An approach to giving equal / same / one-on-one education to everyone is neither realistic nor meaningful. For example, it would be unfair to the detriment of such students to give special education students the same education as everyone else. Social justice in education refers to the ability to freely develop the creative power of the individual based on human differences, that is, to realize emancipatory education (Polat, 2007).

The belief of individuals in the society in justice and equality within the framework of social justice is very important for the health and continuity of that society. The development of social justice understanding will contribute to the establishment of a sense of peace and justice among the individuals that make up the society, thus contributing to the formation of healthy living environments. At this point, the relationship between social justice

and education becomes important. Because individuals' state of having social justice beliefs is directly related to how and to what extent social justice awareness is given during the education process (Demirkaya & Ünal, 2018). In addition, the fact that there are cultural, social, economic, ethnic, racial, and religious differences in the society, the individual needs of each student are different, and the necessity of respecting and tolerating these differences, that is, teaching democracy, requires social justice in schools. Undoubtedly, the most important duty and responsibility in ensuring social justice in schools fall on administrators and teachers. Social justice should be the mainstay of all educators in their efforts to make students global citizens (Bogotch & Shields, 2014).

In the globalization process, the diversity of the differences in the society has revealed the necessity of adopting new values and approaches in education. The increase in population mobility within and between countries, the increase in pluralism in schools because of this increasing mobility, the necessity to prepare children for participation in the democratic process in multicultural societies, and the awareness of the effects of continuing socioeconomic differences on students' academic achievement have led to the focus on social justice practices in education (Furman & Shields, 2003; Rapp, 2002).

All goals and policies related to education should be based on a set of values such as equality, solidarity, and justice (Şişman, 2006). Internationalization in education makes universities more important in terms of social justice. University education broadens individuals' horizons, paves the way for new ideas and plays an active role in shaping the future. Universities emerge as institutions where knowledge is produced, reproduced, and spread. It is one of the main duties of the state to provide an order in which all members of the society can benefit from these environments without discrimination in universities, which provide students with environments where they can gain the necessary equipment to have a professional profession (Kalyon, 2012). Balanced distribution of opportunities and income plays an important role in ensuring social justice, which is one of the elements of the social rule of law (Çetin, 2015). Thus, the motivation of university students in the school environment in line with their belief in social justice will increase. Motivation for university students is extremely important for both students and teachers (Sakallı, Borazan, Korkmaz, & Eser, 2015). As a matter of fact, universities are institutions that shape the future of countries, train various professionals who have an important place in the society, enable the emergence of entrepreneurial individuals, and aim these individuals to be beneficial to the society in every sense.

1.1. Purpose of the Research

The aim of this study is to reveal how university students conceptualize their perceptions of social justice through their views. In this context, the answers to the following research questions were sought.

According to university students:

1. What does social justice mean?
2. What would a socially fair university look like? What are the characteristics of a socially equitable university?
3. If you were to do something to improve social justice in universities, what would you do?
4. Can you tell us about the most unfair event that happened to you in your university life?
5. How can these injustices be prevented?

2. Method

2.1. Research Model

Since the perceptions and meanings of social justice are examined in-depth, the phenomenological design, one of the qualitative research designs, was used in the study. Qualitative data analysis is defined as a process where the researcher organizes the data, analyzes, and synthesizes, reveals patterns, becomes aware of important variables, and decides which

information will be reflected in the report (Bogdan & Biklen, 1992). Phenomenology is the conscious experience of people's own life worlds, that is, their daily life and social action (Schram, 2003). The basis of phenomenology (phenomenology), which is the basis of studies that aim to investigate phenomena that are not completely alien to us, but whose meanings are not fully understood, is that everyone perceives the external world in a unique way (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). In studies carried out with a phenomenological design, the cognitive structures existing in their minds are tried to be revealed by examining the comments of the research participants about the facts they have personally experienced (Creswell, 2014). Phenomenology research is a research design that aims to highlight the perceptions and experiences of individuals from their own point of view (Ersoy, 2016). Phenomenology is an elaborate and in-depth description of how people experience phenomena (Patton, 2014).

2.2. Study Group of the Research

One of the purposeful sampling methods, the easily accessible situation sampling method, was used in determining the study group. With this technique, people who are easily accessible by the researcher are generally used in determining the participants (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). Participants of this study were determined as university students studying at Muş Alparslan University and 446 university students were reached. However, 53 forms that did not express an opinion on social justice were eliminated, as a result, they consisted of 393 people.

Table 1: Demographic Information of the Participants

Variables	Category	N	%
Gender	Female	125	31,7
	Male	268	68,3
The class	1st grade	130	33,1
	2nd grade	92	23,4
	3rd grade	66	16,8
	4th grade	105	26,7
Total Number of Students		393	100

2.3. Collection of Data

In this study, which aims to reach the perceptions of university students studying at Muş Alparslan University on the concept of social justice, a form consisting of two parts was created online. In the first part, they were asked to answer the personal information form asking about demographic characteristics, and in the second part, the structured interview form with five questions. The prepared forms were sent online and collected in the same way.

In this study, data were collected using a structured interview form. The interview form was created after taking the opinions of the experts in this field and scanning this area. In this way, the content validity of the interview form was tried to be increased. There is a section with personal information and a section with interview questions in the interview form. In the section with personal information, the information of the people participating in the research was kept confidential and codes were created. Before starting the research, pilot applications were carried out and the validity of the interview was tested by taking the opinions of the experts and it was seen that there was no problem.

While creating the interview form, firstly, questions were prepared by scanning the literature and taking expert opinions. Later, the form was presented to expert opinion and arranged. A pilot application was carried out with 10 students and the interview form was finalized. In this way, the content validity of the interview form was tried to be ensured. To determine the profiles of the participants in the study, a personal information section was added to the interview form,

but this information was kept confidential by the researcher in accordance with the principle of confidentiality. Five questions were determined in the interview form to be asked to the participant. Interview forms were conducted by seeking answers to questions such as what social justice means, how a fair university is, what the characteristics of a fair university are, what to do to improve social justice, how they talk about the most unfair incident that happened to them and how these injustices can be prevented.

2.4. Data Analysis

Content analysis was used in the analysis of the data obtained in the study. According to Patton (2014), content analysis requires reviewing repetitive words and themes in the text. In other words, content analysis is a term used for efforts to make sense of data by identifying basic meanings and consistencies when evaluating a comprehensive qualitative material. In this research process, it was aimed to reveal the concepts that can best reflect the meaning while coding the meaningful parts obtained from the data. To find themes, common aspects between codes are evaluated and categorized. At this stage, to ensure internal and external consistency, it has been paid attention to whether the emerging themes are different from each other but form a meaningful whole among them. The data obtained by organizing the codes and themes are explained to the reader in a language open to the reader. During the definition and interpretation of the findings, the findings were described in detail and the results were interpreted, and the resulting results were explained, and content analysis was carried out by considering the definitions.

2.5. Validity and Reliability

First, each interview form was coded as S1, S2... for students. In qualitative research, validity and reliability studies are carried out with the processes of credibility, transferability, consistency, and verifiability (Erlandson, Harris, Skipper, & Allen, 1993; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016). Care was taken to ensure that the validity and reliability criteria chosen in this study reflect the different realities in the participants' minds to the research findings in a fair and complete manner.

To ensure credibility, the data collection tool, the raw data obtained because of the interviews, the codes created because of the analysis, and the research results were presented to the examination of an expert in the field of educational sciences.

In ensuring the transferability, Erlandson et al. (1993), the detailed description technique by the emphasis was used. Identification of the participants, collection, and analysis of data is explained in detail. Efforts have been made to ensure transferability by making direct quotations from participants' views to provide a detailed description.

Within the scope of the reliability studies of the research, a consistency analysis was carried out and special attention was paid to ensure verifiability.

3. Results

3.1. Findings Regarding the First Sub-Problem

In this part of the research, the first sub-problem "What does social justice mean for you?" opinions were given depending on the sub-themes related to the sub-problem. Thematic codes created based on the students' views on what social justice means are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Students; "What does social justice mean to you? Opinions on the Question"

Theme	Thematic code	Frequency	Total Frequency
What does social justice mean to you?	Equality	121	378
	Equal rights and freedom	57	
	Equality of opportunity	57	
	Be fair	20	
	Do not violate rights	18	
	Act according to need	10	
	Freedom of thought	9	
	Non-discrimination	9	
	Searching and using your right	6	
	Harmony between individual and society	5	
	Empathy	5	
	Communication	4	
	Common good and order	4	
	Accuracy	4	
	Balance	4	
	Valuing	3	
	Conscience	3	
	Respect	3	
	Togetherness	3	
	Social relationship	3	
	Democracy belief	2	
	Individual	2	
Be nice to the student	2		
Everyone's happiness	2		

When Table 2 is examined, according to university students, social justice; equality, equal rights and freedom, equality of opportunity, acting fairly, not violating rights, acting according to needs, freedom of thought, non-discrimination, seeking and exercising one's right, the harmony of individual and society, empathy, communication, common good and order, righteousness, balance It was found that it refers to facts such as valuing, conscience, respect, togetherness, social relationship, belief in democracy, individual, good treatment of the student, and happiness of everyone. Also, 22 students stated that there is no social justice. Some opinions on the subject are expressed as follows.

S12: "Everyone can get an equal education and be equal in all subjects, seeking and exercising their rights."

S15: "Social justice is to create the order that will enable everyone to continue their lives under equal conditions, considering the situations we are in."

S24: "It means that individuals living in the same society have the same opportunities and are treated with the same treatment. It also expresses that each individual is valuable, and that each individual's interests and needs are met. "

S41: "The whole society is regarded as equal in all respects; it is thought that one is neither inferior nor superior to the other."

S45: "Social justice is to offer everyone an equal, just living standard. A fair life means being egalitarian, having full faith in democracy."

S60: "It is to give everyone what they deserve as it should be. The greatest justice is to do whatever conditions and environments require."

S68: "Social justice means that everyone is educated equally and should benefit from their rights and responsibilities equally."

S149: "Social justice means that individuals in a society have equal rights in areas such as education, health, economy, and politics."

S335: "Social justice means "freedom" for me. Because, where there is injustice, people have limitations in reaching their goals, sustaining their lives, and realizing themselves, and they cannot realize them."

3.2. Findings Regarding the Second Sub-Problem

In this section, "What would a socially fair university look like? What are the characteristics of a socially equitable university?" Opinions were tried to be given depending on the sub-themes of the second sub-problem. Thematic codes created based on students' views on the expression of the socially just university are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Students; "What would a socially fair university look like? What are the characteristics of a socially equitable university?" Opinions on the Question

Theme	Thematic code	Frequency	Total Frequency
What would a socially fair university look like? What are the characteristics of a socially equitable university?	Every student is equal	81	521
	Equal opportunity provided	57	
	Indiscriminate	38	
	Benefited from social activities	33	
	Same rights for every student	30	
	Cares about interests and needs	22	
	Suitable for every student's needs	17	
	Fair to every student	17	
	Same education for every student	16	
	Evaluation according to the student's ability and characteristics	14	
	Without torpedo	13	
	Technological tool support	13	
	Programs to support events	12	
	Have freedom of expression	12	
	Considering the student	11	
	Financial and moral support	11	
	Same conditions as other universities	10	
	Worth every student	10	
Fair teachers	9		

Taking every student's opinion	8
That value ideas	7
Protecting students' rights	6
Who does not despise students	6
Student communication is strong	6
Students from all walks of life will be comfortable	6
Support for every student	5
Empathetic	5
Libertarian	5
Respectful	5
Giving everyone what they deserve	4
Equal importance to every part	4
Solving the student's problems	4
Freedom to use social space	3
Free material for each section	3
Reassuring	3
Fair in scoring	3
Offering what the department requires	2
Independent of politics	2
Conscientious	2
Student supporter	2
Support for socialization	2
Able to distinguish between successful and unsuccessful	2

When Table 3 is examined, it is a socially fair university according to university students; Every student is equal, equal opportunity is provided, there is no discrimination, every student is equally benefited from social activities, every student is given the same rights, interests and needs are cared for, appropriate for each student's needs, every student is treated fairly, every student is the same education, evaluation according to the student's ability and characteristics, No favoritism, technological tool support, programs that support activities, freedom of expression, student-minded, financial and moral support, the same conditions as other universities, valuing every student, fair teachers, taking every student's opinion, valuing ideas, protecting students' rights, despising students It was found that there would be people who were blind. Some opinions on the subject are expressed as follows.

S160: "By providing equal rights and equal social activities to every department."

S166: "In a fair university, every student should be treated equally, and nepotism should not be done according to the department they study."

S182: "A university where every department is treated equally without discrimination and everyone is given equal usage rights."

S231: "A socially fair university: I believe that with its fair management, all employees, educators, students, and staff, who are aware of their responsibilities, can achieve more by fulfilling their job properly. I think the characteristics of a socially fair university are; fair behavior, nepotism, protection of rights, the ability of those who deserve to come to the places they deserve, the presence of competent people in the fields"

they are competent to, equality of opportunity, correct identification of problems and implementation of correct solutions, educating educators and students who are competent in education and training concepts, especially " To prevent the concept of "torpedo" being used both verbally and as dhikr, it is to prevent the parts of this concept that are used in the verb.

S233: *"Everyone should be supported with a support program suitable for their own conditions. It is important to establish sincere dialogues with students to eliminate the gap between students. Eating, drinking, and education expenses should be supported by all the facilities of the school. The scholarship may not be available to all students. The school should have its own scholarship program. And the scholarships should be free. "*

S296: *"Every student should be treated equally, every student's problems should be helped, psychologically helped."*

S351: *"A socially fair university should be a space where individuals can freely express their opinions and thoughts."*

S393: *"The university, which recognizes that student differences are taken into consideration and that not everyone can read under equal conditions, and tries to correct this, provides social justice to some extent."*

3.3. Findings Regarding the Third Sub-Problem

In this section, "What would you do if you were to do something to improve social justice in universities?" Opinions were tried to be given depending on the sub-themes related to the third sub-problem. Thematic codes created based on the opinions of the students regarding the statement of what to do to improve social justice are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Students; "What would you do if you were to do something to improve social justice in universities?"
Opinions on the Question

Theme	Thematic code	Frequency	Total Frequency
What would you do if you were to do something to improve social justice in universities?	Social activities	44	325
	Ensuring equality	32	
	Financial support	31	
	Providing the same opportunities for everyone	20	
	Learning student ideas	19	
	Raising awareness of management and teachers	16	
	Be fair	14	
	Indiscrimination	12	
	Listen to all students' problems	11	
	Determination of interest and needs	10	
	Solving student problems	10	
	Right to speak to students	9	
	Ensuring freedom of expression	9	
	Group activities	9	
	Technological tool support	8	
Increasing teacher-student interaction	8		
Reaching all individuals	8		

Reducing the differences between other universities	7
Do not empathize	6
Ensuring student satisfaction	6
Understanding for students	6
Organizing sessions with important figures	5
Observing student rights	5
Social areas	5
Freedom	3
Audit	3
Increasing the quality of academicians	3
Getting a job	2
Including students in management	2
Conscientiousness	2

When Table 4 is examined, the findings regarding what university students can do to improve social justice are as follows: Social activities, ensuring equality, financial aid, providing the same opportunities to everyone, learning student ideas, raising awareness of management and teachers, acting fairly, not discriminating, listening to the problems of all students, identifying interests and needs, solving student problems, giving students the right to speak, providing freedom of expression, group activities, technological tool support, increasing teacher-student interaction, reaching all individuals, reducing the differences with other universities, empathizing. Some of the opinions expressed on the subject are as follows.

S18: "I would reduce the lesson hours and do things to increase the interaction between the student and the teacher."

S186: "I would ensure that the person is treated equally, regardless of the high position of the person, and I would raise the awareness of the authorized people about this."

S216: "First of all, I would design programs where all students in the university will be encouraged and have fun with knowledgeable and quality times."

S233: "I would identify needy students and bring them to a position where they could have at least the same opportunities as other students. I would try to support both financially and culturally. "

S346: "I would try to meet all the financial and moral needs of the students. Because meeting the basic needs of the student is a priority. Without meeting these needs, the student cannot fully focus on the education life."

3.4. Findings Regarding the Fourth Sub-Problem

In this section, "Could you tell us about the most unfair incident in your university life?" For the fourth sub-problem, university students were given opinions according to their sub-themes. Thematic codes formed based on the opinions of the students regarding the unfair incident statement you have experienced are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Students; "Can you tell us about the most unfair event that happened to you in your university life?"
Opinions on the Question

Theme	Thematic code	Frequency	Total Frequency
Can you tell us about the most unfair event that happened to you in your university life?	Distance education obligation due to the pandemic	32	176
	Getting the score, I do not deserve	26	
	Discrimination	23	
	Lack of fairness in scoring	17	
	Unfair scholarship distribution	6	
	No course exemption	5	
	Technical problems	5	
	Inadequacy of the instructor entering the lesson	4	
	Being despised for different thoughts	4	
	Being mobbed	4	
	Be scolded for nothing	4	
	Not having the same opportunities	3	
	Not being treated fairly	3	
	Lack of understanding for necessary reasons	3	
	To be tried for wearing	3	
	Being exposed to prejudice	3	
	Not aiding the needy	3	
	Reflecting events on a note	3	
	No reward	2	
	Do not keep the employee and the one who does not work	2	
	Being weaker than other universities	2	
	Lack of application opportunity	2	
	Being blamed for something I have not done	2	
	Disrespect of the teachers	2	
	Lack of speech	2	
	Being exposed to the lesson and teacher I have not chosen	1	
	Failing lesson for minutes	1	
	Difference between departments	1	
	Grade system	1	
	Selecting the representative by the teacher	1	
	Missing chapter books in the library	1	
	Same type of teaching to learners in different ways	1	
The office of unqualified persons	1		
Disabled people not being privileged	1		
Treating those sitting in the back like mischief	1		
Staying when I should not be absent	1		

When Table 5 is analyzed, the most unfair incident that happened to university students; expressed the necessity of distance education due to the pandemic, getting an undeserved score, discrimination, lack of justice in scoring, unfair scholarship distribution, no course exemption, and technical problems. Some of the opinions expressed on the subject are as follows.

S34: "Teachers keeping employees and non-employees at the same level"

S59: "Teachers behave biased, different teachers not forcing one class while another teacher does not force another class in elective courses, and there is an unbalanced scoring between two classes, teachers evaluate homework without any evaluation criteria while assigning the same task to everyone, and the employee and the employee get the same score, or the employee falls below the non-working person. "

S63: "My teacher gives more points to another activity even though he chose the activity as the best activity as he said. Our teacher does not behave equally among my classmates and I do not feel worthless. "

S107: "In this pandemic process we are experiencing right now, even though everyone does not have a comfortable home environment and trouble-free internet and technological tools, it is important to continue education in this way and to take the exam, homework, etc. being subjected is the greatest injustice I have experienced in my university life. In addition, the biggest injustice in my university life is that I coincide with a period where everything is valued but education is not valued. "

S175: "A teacher who hurt me because I am studying at my second university is saying that you cannot come to school and finish school."

S231: "I applied to work part-time. Although I did not receive any scholarships or loans, I needed them very much and I started this during the interview phase, but it was one of the most unfair situations I have encountered in the university, and this is not just me. It happened to a few of my friends the same year. "

S264: "I could not answer because the microphone was broken during the live lesson. When someone else answered, he got +10 points for the final grade."

S281: "I can say that what I am living now unfairly is education due to the pandemic. I would love to have live lessons. It would both contribute to me academically and to learn something. Some friends live in the countryside and cannot access the internet, so live classes are not held. I consider it a great injustice to try to learn by reading myself with documents. We have valuable teachers. If we cannot get face-to-face training from them, I would love to study at least with live lessons. This makes me sad. "

S306: "While a friend of mine who is studying at the same department with me at another university can increase his interest in his departments by doing experiments in a virtual laboratory established by his teachers over the internet, in my department there are surprise lectures or grades taken without meeting with the student, we have teachers unaware of their students. I just want to read the chapter properly. This is my only wish to be able to understand the lessons not by randomly memorized notes but by digesting them. "

S335: "Since I am a disabled person, my situation is not taken into account due to my disability in my arm and I will not be constantly exposed to injustice about the way and duration of the exams."

3.5. Findings Regarding the Fifth Sub-Problem

In this section, "How can these injustices be prevented? Can you share your views? " Opinions were given depending on the sub-themes related to the fifth sub-problem. Thematic codes created based on the opinions of the students on how to prevent injustices are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Students; "How can these injustices be prevented? Can you share your views?" Opinions on the Question

Theme	Thematic code	Frequency	Total Frequency
How can these injustices be prevented? Can you share your views?	Treating everyone equally	26	297
	If equal opportunities are provided for everyone	18	
	By switching to face-to-face training	18	
	By empathy	14	
	Without discrimination	14	
	Acting fairly	13	
	Paying attention to student thoughts	13	
	Caring for each individual	13	
	By improving teacher student relations	13	
	With the education system	10	
	Consciences resting	10	
	By bringing in competent persons	9	
	Dealing with student problems	8	
	By training the teachers	8	
	Understanding	7	
	With the right managers	7	
	By improving the humanity of people	6	
	Control	6	
	Paying attention to love and respect	6	
	Considering student requests	6	
	Defending your right	5	
	Respecting different thoughts	5	
	By not being unfair	5	
	Thinking that everyone's circumstances are different	5	
	With more activities	5	
	Using common sense	5	
	Not doing the behavior we do not want ourselves to do	5	
	By removing the unfair from the system	4	
	If everyone does his duty properly	3	
	Breaking prejudices	3	
With financial support	3		
Doing the right thing even if it goes against your interests	3		
Taking responsibility	3		
If everyone likes their job	2		
Neutrally	2		
By ensuring freedom of expression	2		

Respecting labor	2
By seeing and not ignoring	2
Unnecessarily	2
In good faith	1
By awarding	1
With effort	1
By producing solutions	1
With penalties and sanctions	1
By improving yourself	1

When Table 6 is examined, the statements of university students on how to prevent injustice are as follows: Treating everyone equally, providing equal opportunities to everyone, starting face-to-face education, establishing empathy, non-discrimination, being fair, valuing student thoughts, giving importance to each individual, developing teacher-student relations, they expressed their views as listening to the conscience and bringing competent people. Some opinions on the subject are expressed as follows.

S37: "In a world where there are respect and love and no favoritism, there will be justice."

S44: "The more conscious individuals are and the more empathy they develop, the less injustice will be. We must read and become conscious. We should not do something that we do not want ourselves to do to someone else. I think the event is about how conscious we are and as a society we should attach great importance to this issue."

S83: "It cannot be prevented. No matter how many suggestions I make, my writing always remains in the discourse. Peyami Safa has a very nice saying that does not act. I wish everyone could internalize it "It is easier to blame than to understand. Because if you understand, you must change." people prefer to blame rather than renew and update themselves, but they are the losers. However, people who accept their mistakes and learn from them are individuals who have discovered themselves and have been able to define themselves. "

S105: "It is necessary to gather everyone's opinion on a certain denominator, to open a presentation in a pool, to declare the responsibilities, and to take action."

S241: "This injustice can only be prevented by solving the original injustice. Torpedo is prevented when nepotism is over and when people who do their job properly are in the positions they deserve. "

S393: "Ensuring justice is above all a matter of conscience. Therefore, it is necessary to be a conscientious individual and society first. After that, it is necessary to meet the needs of every individual fairly."

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

"What does social justice mean for you?", "What would a socially fair university look like?" What are the characteristics of a socially just university?", "What would you do if you were to do something to improve social justice in universities?", "Can you tell the most unfair incident in your university life?", "How can these injustices be prevented? Can you share your views? " Their answers to open-ended questions were evaluated. The social justice of the university students participating in the research is mostly; Equality, equal rights and freedom, equality of opportunity, fair treatment, not violating rights, acting according to needs, freedom of thought, and non-discrimination. In addition, in the responses obtained, it was determined that the students interpreted social justice with expressions that can be evaluated within the scope of social justice principles, social minimum, equal citizenship, equal opportunity, fair distribution principles of David Miller's (2005). With the results of the study,

Miller's approach to social justice is supported. In addition, it was determined that the students used the concepts of social justice and equality together. This perception points to the concept of egalitarian social justice. Bursa (2015) found in his study that most of the participants defined social justice as justice and equality. Based on this, it can be said that the concepts of equality and social justice are intertwined. İdin and Aydoğdu (2017) also reached similar findings in their studies.

In his study, Yıldırım (2011) emphasized that university students should be equal, benefit all individuals equally without discrimination, equal opportunities in education, and an egalitarian free society. It also found that they define social justice generally in the context of equal opportunity. Accordingly, Turhan (2007) emphasizes the necessity of regulating Turkish education system policies in a way that either refuses or eliminates the differences.

In the research, a socially fair university according to university students; It was stated that every student will be a place where equal opportunities are provided, there is no discrimination, social activities are equally benefited, every student is given the same rights, interests, and needs are cared for, and every student will be treated fairly. Polat (2007), in his study on social justice in school, mentions that school administrators are responsible for the realization of social justice at school. According to Chiu and Walker (2007), school administrators should demonstrate leadership that solves injustice and inequality in school to ensure social justice in the school.

University students' views on what can be done to improve social justice; social activities, providing equality, financial aid, providing the same opportunities to everyone, learning student ideas, raising awareness of management and teachers, acting fairly, non-discrimination, listening to all students' problems, determining interests and needs, solving student problems, right to speak to students, expression providing freedom, group activities, technological tool support, increasing teacher-student interaction, reaching all individuals and reducing the differences between other universities. Similarly, Akkuş (2019) in his research; In order to improve social justice in schools, students should be treated more fairly, student opinions should be consulted, attention should be paid to student demands, equal opportunities and opportunities should be provided, infrastructure should be equalized, physical and financial opportunities should be equalized in schools, more financial support should be given to students in need, it has reached the conclusion that everyone should be treated equally.

The most unfair thing that happened to university students; They expressed the necessity of distance education due to the pandemic, getting an undeserved score, discrimination, lack of justice in scoring, unfair scholarship distribution, and no course exemption. Dündar's (2010) issue of the conversion of equality in education and at work in the example of post-modern context, Turkey has identified 54 documents examined. He examined the students' having equal opportunities in the process. In this context, He emphasized that factors such as teacher quality, equipment quality, transportation facilities, and use of technology, school culture, orientation processes, psychological and social support, investments, and environment are included in the scope of equality in education. McConney and Perry (2010) determined in their study that more equal socio-economic conditions should be provided to schools to increase student success.

The statements of university students on how to prevent injustice are as follows. By treating everyone equally, if everyone is provided with equal opportunities, by transitioning to face-to-face education, by establishing empathy, not discriminating, treating fairly, caring for student thoughts, caring for each individual, developing teacher-student relations, by listening to conscience, by bringing competent people. The students stated that they should be treated fairly but being fair does not mean treating everyone the same. Being fair requires positive discrimination (Akkuş, 2019). Students emphasized the necessity of positive discrimination in ensuring social justice. While some students want to be given as much as they deserve based on performance, it is understood that they favor positive discrimination. Tomul (2009), in his study with 147 school administrators, identified the obstacles that negatively affect social justice practices and social justice in schools. As a result of the study, it has been determined that the most important obstacle in front of the works aimed at ensuring social justice is seen as

the lack of resources. Polat (2007), based on the distribution of teachers among schools in Turkey, there are disparities in the distribution of financial resources and physical infrastructure. Filiz (2020), Turkey and both countries in a study comparing Spain state's role in ensuring social justice, and it is a great responsibility, it is emphasized that an unbiased way as a mechanism to ensure equality and justice. In addition, the study found that the concept of injustice in the perception of most individuals is identified with economic and political systematic problems. While individuals define social justice in the ideal environment, they use the concept of social justice; When they talked about the injustices in their own life experiences while attributing to the changes in the individual sphere, to the fairness and behavior of others, they complained about many problems with the political and economic system, such as the unequal division of labor in society, and unfair economic distribution. In order to solve all these problems, the state should provide democratic attitude and moral maturity to all individuals in cooperation with school and family from an early age (Akan & Tatik, 2020). Thus, students will be trained with the awareness of moral values and democracy starting from basic education. As a matter of fact, while the understanding of democracy is treating everyone equally in practices, moral values will direct people to behave justly.

In terms of ensuring social justice based on the results of the research; Club activities that can improve social justice in schools can be emphasized. It may be suggested to give activities involving the concepts of social justice with undergraduate courses or elective courses on social justice. Policies can be produced to improve the conditions of schools in the disadvantaged regions of Turkey and to compete on equal terms. This research was conducted using qualitative research methods. In addition, studies can be carried out with quantitative or mixed methods. This study is a research conducted at the higher education level. Research can be done at different levels. A scale can be developed regarding the social justice perception levels of students studying in higher education.

References

- Akan, Y., & Tatik, R. S. (2020). Relationship between students' moral maturity, democratic attitude and target behaviour development levels: A correlational study. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 12(4), 1-20. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15345/iojes.2020.04.001>
- Akkuş, Ş. (2019). *Okullarda sosyal adaletin geliştirilmesine ilişkin yönetici, öğretmen ve öğrenci görüşleri*. (Unpublished master's thesis), Gaziantep Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Gaziantep.
- Barker, R. L. (1999). *The social work dictionary*. Washington DC: NASW Press.
- Bell, L.A. (2007). Theoretical foundation for social justice education. M. Adams, L.A. Bell, and P. Griffin (Eds), *In Teaching for Diversity and Social Justice* (1-14). London, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Bogdan, R. C., & Biklen, S K. (1992). *Qualitative research in education*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- Bogotch, I. & Shields, C.M. (2014). Introduction: Do promises of social justice trump paradigms of educational leadership? I, Bogotch and C.M. Shields (Ed.), *In International Handbook of Educational Leadership and Social Justice Volume 1* (s. 1-12). New York: Springer.
- Boyles, D., Carusi, T., & Attick, D. (2009). Historical and critical interpretations of social justice. W. Ayers, T. Quinn, & D. Stoval (Ed.), *In Handbook of Social Justice in Education* (s. 30-42). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Bursa, S. (2015). *Sosyal bilgiler öğretmenlerinin sosyal adalet algı ve deneyimleri*. (Unpublished master's thesis), Anadolu Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eskişehir.
- Chiu, M. M., & Walker, A. (2007). Leadership for social justice in Hong Kong schools: Addressing mechanisms of inequality. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 45(6), 724-739.
- Craig, G. (2002). Poverty, social work, and social justice. *British Journal of Social Work*, 32, 669-682.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Araştırma deseni*. (S. B. Demir, Trans. Ed.). Ankara: Eğiten Kitap.
- Çetin, H. (2015). Sosyal adalet, sosyal hizmetler ve bütçe. *Toplum ve Sosyal Hizmet*, 26(2), 145-157.
- Demirkaya, H. & Ünal, O. (2018). Sosyal bilgiler öğretmen adaylarının kamu hizmeti motivasyonu algıları ve sosyal adalet idealleri. *Turkish Studies*, 13(4), 455-474. <http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.7827/Turkishstudies.13016>.
- Dündar, S. (2010). *Eğitimde fırsatların eşitliği ve post moderndeki dönüşümü: Türkiye örneği*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation), Marmara Üniversitesi, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Erlanson, D.A., Harris, E.L., Skipper, B.L., & Allen, S.D. (1993). *Doing naturalistic inquiry: A guide to methods*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.

- Ersoy, A. F. (2016). *Fenomenoloji*. Ahmet Saban ve Ali Ersoy (Eds.), *In Eğitimde Nitel Araştırma Desenleri* (51-111), Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık.
- Filiz, B. (2020). *Avrupa Birliği'nde aktif sosyal politikalar ve sosyal adalet algısı: Türkiye ve İspanya üzerine karşılaştırmalı bir analiz*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation), Ankara Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü. Ankara.
- Furman, G. C. & Shields, C. M. (2003, April). How can educational leaders promote and support social justice and democratic community in schools? *Paper presented at Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association*, Chicago, USA.
- İdin, Ş. & Aydoğdu, C. (2017). Fen bilimleri öğretmenlerinin sosyal adalet ve eşitlik perspektifinde fen bilimleri eğitimine ilişkin görüşleri. *Abant İzzet Baysal Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 17 (3), 1328-1349.
- Kalyon, H. (2012). Bülent Ecevit Üniversitesi'nde engelli öğrenci biriminin yeniden yapılandırılması. *Journal of Higher Education & Science*, 2(1), 63. doi:10.5961/jhes.2012.035
- Kaynak, R. Ç. (2017). Social justice, equality, and social work. *Gümüşhane University Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(4): 252 – 260.
- McConney, A. & Perry, L. B. (2010). Science and mathematics achievement in Australia: The role of school socioeconomic composition in educational equity and effectiveness. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 8, 429-452.
- Miller, D. (2005). *What is social justice*. N. Pearce, and W. Paxton (Eds.), *In Social justice: Building Fairer Britain* (5-7). Politico's.
- Patton, M. Q. (2014). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. Sage publications.
- Polat, S. (2007). *Eğitim politikalarının sosyal adalet açısından sonuçları konusunda yönetici ve öğretmen görüşleri*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation), Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü. Ankara.
- Rapp, D. (2002). Social justice and the importance of rebellious imaginations. *Journal of School Leadership*, 12(3), 226-245.
- Sakallı, F., Borazan, A., Korkmaz, E. & Eser, M. (2015). The Motivation Levels of the Students Towards Mathematics Lessons: Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University Pazarcık Vocational High School. *International Journal of Scientific and Technological Research*, 1(4), 15-21.
- Schram, T. H. (2003). *Conceptualizing qualitative inquiry*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Sunal, O. (2011). Sosyal politika: Sosyal adalet açısından kuramsal bir değerlendirme. *Ankara Üniversitesi SBF Dergisi*, 66 (83), 283-305.
- Şişman, M. (2006, Nov.). Eğitimde demokrasi ve sosyal adalet: Türkiye eğitim sisteminin değişmeyen miti. *Türk Eğitim Sisteminde Yeni Paradigma Arayışları*. Eğitimciler Birliği Sendikası (Eğitim-Bir-Sen), Ankara.
- Todd, S. (2015). Social justice and social action: Organizing for change. L. Dominelli (Com.), Social work subsection. *In International Encyclopedia of Social and Behavioral Sciences*. London: Elsevier
- Tomul, E. (2009). İlköğretim okullarındaki sosyal adalet uygulamalarına ilişkin yönetici görüşleri. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 34(152).
- Turhan, M. (2007). *Genel ve mesleki lise yöneticilerinin etik liderlik davranışlarının okullardaki sosyal adalet üzerindeki etkisi*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation), Fırat Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Elazığ.
- Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek H. (2016). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri*. Ankara: Seçkin Yayınevi.
- Yıldırım, F. (2011). Üniversite gençliği "sosyal adalet" ten ne anlıyor? Sosyal adalet ilkelerinin sosyal adalet algısı üzerindeki etkisi. *Sosyal Politika Çalışmaları Dergisi*, 25 (25), 113-124. <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/spcd/issue/21104/227287>
- World Bank (2010). *World Development Indicators 2010*. Washington: USA.